

LEADERSHIP COMPETENCE AND CHALLENGES OF SCHOOL HEADS IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OF THE CITY OF ILAGAN: BASIS FOR UPGRADING INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the leadership competence and challenges encountered by school heads in public elementary schools within the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, in terms of the five domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH). It aimed to assess the competence levels of school heads as perceived by both themselves and their teachers, determine the extent of challenges faced, and explore the relationship between their profile variables and leadership performance. Using a descriptive survey design, the study involved 75 school heads and 300 randomly selected teachers. Data were gathered through a validated questionnaire based on the PPSSH. Descriptive statistics and inferential tools such as ANOVA and Pearson r were used to analyze the data. Findings revealed that most school heads were aged 41–48, predominantly female, held positions as Head Teachers or Teachers-in-Charge, had over 10 years of experience, and led small schools. Overall, they were rated competent across all PPSSH domains, with notable strengths in vision promotion, financial management, and recognition systems. However, areas like school planning, research innovation, instructional supervision, and communication showed room for growth. Challenges were generally manageable, with moderate concerns in leadership development, records management, and managing diverse learners. The study concluded that while school heads demonstrate core leadership competencies, certain areas require targeted support. The findings underscore the need for sustained professional development and an upgraded intervention program to enhance leadership effectiveness and improve educational outcomes in the division.

Keywords: *Leadership competence, challenges encountered, Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH), upgraded intervention program, professional development, public elementary schools, City of Ilagan*

INTRODUCTION

School administrators serve as the cornerstone of the educational system, playing a pivotal role in driving the school's vision and mission. They wield the authority, responsibility, and accountability necessary to nurture the well-being of individuals within the school while simultaneously optimizing organizational performance and health. This multifaceted role involves setting the direction for schools, managing systems and processes, fostering quality teaching and learning, nurturing personal and professional growth, and engaging stakeholders in initiatives aimed at enhancing school communities. The success or failure of a school largely hinges on the effectiveness of its administrators.

However, public elementary school heads face an array of challenges that often impede their ability to lead effectively. Among these is the management of scarce resources, which limits their capacity to provide sufficient facilities, instructional materials, and technological support. Overcrowded classrooms, insufficient funding, and outdated infrastructure further exacerbate these issues. Administrative responsibilities often overshadow strategic leadership and instructional supervision, leaving limited time to focus on critical aspects such as curriculum innovation, teacher mentoring, and student-centered initiatives. Moreover, administrators must navigate socio-cultural and economic complexities, including addressing the needs of learners from marginalized communities, mitigating the effects of poverty on education, and fostering meaningful engagement with parents and stakeholders who may have limited participation in school activities.

In line with these, the Department of Education (DepEd) has recognized the critical role of school heads in achieving educational excellence. Policies such as DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020, emphasize the need for school heads to develop competencies aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH). Additionally, Republic Act 9155, known as the Governance of Basic Education Act, aims to empower school leaders to meet the evolving demands of education. RA 9155 underscores also the authority and responsibility of school heads in managing their institutions, highlighting their role in ensuring effective instructional leadership and school management. Likewise, DepEd Memorandum No. 50, s. 2020, provides guidelines on the development of school leaders, highlighting capacity-building initiatives to improve instructional leadership, school management, and policy implementation. These policies align with the need for continuous leadership development to address the ever-evolving challenges in education.

In the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, public elementary school heads face significant challenges, such as managing overcrowded classrooms, inadequate funding, outdated infrastructure, and limited access to teaching materials and technology. These resource constraints, along with the increasing demands for compliance with educational policies and regulations, create an environment where school heads must juggle multiple

responsibilities. They must oversee school operations, address the socio-cultural needs of their communities, foster professional growth among teachers, and engage parents and other stakeholders, often with insufficient time and resources. The weight of these challenges can impede the development of leadership competencies necessary for effective school management and instructional leadership.

Thus, leadership competence is crucial for school heads in addressing these challenges and achieving the educational goals of their schools. Effective leadership involves not only managing resources and ensuring compliance with policies but also guiding teachers in their professional development, mentoring staff, and making decisions that directly impact student learning. However, many school heads in the Division struggle to fulfill these roles due to a lack of adequate training, insufficient support, and the overwhelming demands of their positions. The gap between the leadership competencies required by school heads and the challenges they face calls for a comprehensive examination of the factors that affect their ability to lead effectively.

The researcher's firsthand exposure to the realities of school leadership has provided a unique perspective on these challenges. Through interactions with school heads, the researcher has observed not only the external constraints they encounter but also their internal struggles—maintaining morale, sustaining motivation, and realizing their vision for the school amidst relentless demands. These observations have fueled the researcher's passion to delve deeper into understanding these challenges, motivated by a strong commitment to supporting educational leadership as a vital driver of quality education for all learners.

As a former Teacher-in-Charge (TIC) and newly promoted Head Teacher (HT), the researcher has firsthand experience navigating the complexities of school leadership, having managed school operations while simultaneously fulfilling teaching duties. This dual role revealed the immense challenges school heads face, such as balancing administrative responsibilities, maintaining instructional quality, and addressing the diverse needs of students, teachers, and stakeholders. Promotion to HT further emphasized difficulties in program implementation, financial management, and stakeholder engagement. These experiences, along with interactions with fellow school heads, inspired the researcher to pursue this study, driven by a strong belief in the importance of understanding and addressing leadership challenges. The study sought to contribute valuable insights into the common issues faced by school heads in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan and aims to provide evidence-based recommendations for upgrading interventions that enhance leadership competencies across the five domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH), which define the essential skills required for effective school leadership.

By examining the leadership competence and challenges of school heads in this study, the researcher aimed to provide valuable insights that led to the design of upgraded intervention. This intervention was rooted in the realities of school leadership, addressing both the internal and external factors that affect the performance of school heads.

Research Questions

This study examines the leadership competence and the challenges encountered by the School Head in public elementary schools in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, using the findings as a foundation for creating an upgraded intervention.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the School Head respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Gender
 - c. Position Title
 - d. Number of Years as School Head
 - e. Highest Level of Education
 - f. Type of School
 - g. Leadership Related Trainings for the last five years.
2. How competent are the School Heads as perceived by them and the teachers vis-à-vis:
 - a. Leading Strategically
 - b. Managing Operations and Resources
 - c. Focusing on teaching and Learning
 - d. Developing Self and Others
 - e. Building Connection
3. Is there a significant difference on the leadership competence of the School Heads as perceived by them and the teachers?
4. Is there a significant difference on the leadership competence of the School Heads when grouped according to their profile?
5. How serious are the challenges encountered by the School Heads in the performance of their duties and responsibilities along the five domains of the PPSSH?
6. Is there a significant difference on the challenges encountered by the School heads in the performance of their duties and responsibilities when grouped according to their profile?
7. Do the challenges encountered by the School Heads significantly affect their leadership competence?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive survey method. According to Sevilla et al. (1992), this method is used when one attempts to analyze, interpret, and report the present status of the subject. The descriptive survey method was utilized to gather and analyze data on leadership competencies and challenges encountered by the elementary School Heads.

By incorporating the perspectives of both School Heads and teachers, this method offered a comprehensive view of the current leadership practices and challenges. The findings served as a basis for recommending interventions to enhance leadership competencies and address areas for improvement.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in the 6 districts of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan comprising a total of 79 elementary schools with a total of 75 School Heads and 710 elementary teachers. Schools Division of the City of Ilagan is an offshoot of the conversion of the Municipality of Ilagan in the Province of Isabela into a component City, which was approved by the former Secretary of Education Armin A Luistro, FSC on December 17, 2012 in pursuant to Section 48 of Republic Act 10169. The SDO City of Ilagan is now on its 12 years since establishment offering complete basic education from Kindergarten to Grade 12.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of this study were the 75 School Heads and 300 teachers of the public elementary schools of the Schools Division of the City Ilagan. The total population of 75 elementary school heads were taken as respondents while the sample size for teachers was determined using Slovin's formula. This formula ensures that a representative sample is selected while minimizing sampling error. After the sample size was computed, the teachers were selected through the draw-lots method to ensure randomization and fairness in the selection process. This approach guaranteed that all teachers have equal chance of being included in the study.

The table below shows the distribution of the respondents in the six districts.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

District	Number of Teachers	Sample Size	No. of School Heads	Total
East	44	19	6	25
South	160	68	12	80
West	123	52	11	63
North	138	58	16	74
North-West	142	60	15	75
San Antonio	103	43	15	58
Total	710	300	75	375

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering process begun with a formal request for approval from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan. The

request outlined the objectives of the study, the intended data collection methods, and the involvement of school heads and teachers as key respondents. Upon receiving approval, the researcher coordinated with the district in-charge notifying them about the study and explained its scope, emphasizing the importance of their cooperation in facilitating the process. The district in-charge helped communicate the study's goals to the school heads, ensuring that they are well-informed.

Next, an orientation session was organized for the school heads, where the researcher provided an overview of the study's purpose, the structure of the survey, and the roles of the school heads and teachers in the data collection process. School heads were instrumental in distributing the questionnaires to the teachers, ensuring proper communication of the study's aims and timeline. The sample of teachers were selected through a randomized draw-lots method, based on a sample size determined using Slovin's formula. This ensured fairness and randomness in the selection of teacher-respondents.

Once the teacher-respondents are identified, the survey questionnaires were distributed, accompanied by clear instructions on how to complete them. Ample time has given for respondents to answer thoughtfully and accurately. After the questionnaires have been completed, the researcher collected them, ensuring a high response rate through follow-up communications as needed. The collected data underwent a thorough validation process to check for completeness and consistency before being encoded for analysis. This comprehensive and systematic approach to data gathering ensured that the process is well-organized, transparent, and aligned with ethical standards, thereby contributing to the reliability and validity of the study's findings.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data gathered for the study, the following statistical tools were employed.

Frequency and Percentage Count. This was used to answer the problems on the profile of the respondents.

Weighted Mean. This was used to determine the perceptions of leadership competence and the seriousness of challenges encountered by school heads in performing their duties across the five domains of the PPSSH.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This was used to analyze the significant difference in leadership competence as perceived by school heads and teachers, as well as to examine the differences in leadership competence among school heads when grouped according to their profiles, and to assess the significant differences in the challenges encountered by school heads in performing their duties and responsibilities based on their profiles.

Pearson R Test. This was used to determine whether the challenges encountered by school heads significantly impacted their leadership competence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the respondents' profile in terms of:
 - a. Age

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Age

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
25-32	0	0
33-40	2	2.67
41-48	28	37.33
49-56	25	33.33
57-65	20	26.67
Total	75	100.00

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of age.

As shown in the table, twenty-eight respondents or 37.33 percent are within the 41- 48 age group. Twenty-five respondents or 33.33 percent fall under the 49 -56 age group, while twenty respondents or 26.67 percent are aged 57 -65.

The data reflects that majority of school heads fall under 41-48 age bracket, this is due to the typical age distribution expected of school heads in the Philippines, where leadership roles are usually assumed by educators who have accumulated significant teaching and administrative experience.

DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2007, applicants for Principal I positions must meet specific eligibility criteria, including at least five years of cumulative experience in instructional leadership and teaching, a bachelor's degree in education or its equivalent, at least 120 hours of relevant training, and a performance rating of Very Satisfactory for the last two rating periods. These requirements inherently favor individuals in their forties or older who have had more time to meet these qualifications. This explains the minimal representation of respondents below the age of 41 and highlights how professional prerequisites shape the age demographics of school leadership.

The findings of the present study affirm the study of Carreon (2018), which found that school leadership positions in the Philippines are largely occupied by individuals aged

41 and above, reflecting the importance placed on experience and tenure in the appointment of school heads.

b. Gender

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Gender

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	35	46.67
Female	40	53.33
Total	75	100.00

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of gender.

Table reveals that 40 respondents or 53.33 percent are female while 35 respondents or 46.67 percent are male. This indicates that the majority of the respondents are female out of the total 75.

The higher number of female respondents can be attributed that the teaching profession in the Philippines, particularly in basic education, is predominantly composed of women. This trend is evident in many public schools, where more females enter and stay in the teaching profession compared to their male counterparts.

This finding is supported by the study of Nuqui and Cruz (2020), which stated that the feminization of the teaching workforce in the Philippine education system is a long-standing trend, especially in elementary and secondary schools. Likewise, the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020) consistently reports a higher percentage of female teachers in the Department of Education, reflecting gender preferences and societal roles that influence career choices in the education sector.

c. Position Title

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Position Title

POSITION TITLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Teacher-In-Charge	16	21.33
Head Teacher I	14	18.67
Head Teacher II	0	0.00
Head Teacher III	22	29.33
Principal I	9	12.00
Principal II	10	13.33
Principal III	2	2.67

Principal IV	2	2.67
Total	75	100

The table shows the respondents' distribution by position title: Head Teacher-III (22 or 29.33%), Teacher-In-Charge (16 or 21.33%), Head Teacher-I (14 or 18.67%), Principal-II (10 or 13.33%), Principal-I (9 or 12.00%), and both Principal-III and Principal-IV (2 or 2.67% each), with no respondent holding the Head Teacher-II position. The predominance of Head Teacher-III and Teacher-In-Charge reflects the division's structure, where leadership roles are given to teacher-leaders or officers-in-charge, particularly in schools lacking full-time principals. This mirrors the DepEd practice of appointing senior teachers to such roles in small or multi-grade schools. The finding supports Tabirara (2019), who observed that many Philippine public schools, especially in rural areas, are led by Teacher-In-Charge or Head Teachers due to limited plantilla positions for principals. It also aligns with DepEd's strategy of using temporary leadership to address leadership gaps. The Second Congressional Commission (2025) further highlights the nationwide shortage of school principals, stressing the need for experienced leaders in these critical roles.

d. Number of Years as School Head

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Number of Years as School Head

POSITION TITLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1-3	12	16.00
4-6	6	8.00
7-9	11	14.67
10 and above	46	61.33
Total	75	100.00

Table 5 presents the distribution of respondents by years of service as school head: 46 (61.33%) have served for 10 years or more, 12 (16%) for 1-3 years, 11 (14.67%) for 7-9 years, and 6 (8%) for 4-6 years. This indicates that most respondents possess extensive leadership experience. Within the Department of Education (DepEd), this aligns with DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2007, which requires Principal I applicants to have at least five years of instructional and managerial experience. The study's results show that many respondents far exceed this standard, suggesting that their experience may positively impact school performance, policy implementation, and mentoring. However, the presence of school heads with fewer than six years of experience highlights the importance of leadership training and succession planning. These findings echo Malaluan et al. (2023), whose study found that most public elementary school heads in the Philippines had over ten years of experience, enhancing their competence in school management and stakeholder engagement.

e. Highest Level of Education

Table 6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Highest Level of Education

HIGHEST LEVEL OF EDUCATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
BEED	30	40.00
BSE	1	1.33
BSIE	1	1.33
MAEd	34	45.33
PhD	9	12.00
Total	75	100.00

The table presents the respondents' highest educational attainment: 34 (45.33%) hold a Master of Arts in Education (MAEd), 30 (40%) possess a Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED), and 9 (12%) have earned a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD). This indicates that many school heads have pursued graduate studies. The data shows that most respondents meet or exceed DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2007, which requires a bachelor's degree for Head Teachers and at least a master's degree for Principal I positions. Notably, 57.33% of respondents (MAEd and PhD holders) surpass these qualifications. This level of academic attainment supports school heads in effectively managing instructional leadership, curriculum, and governance. The findings align with Tumibay et al. (2023), who reported that school administrators with graduate degrees demonstrate greater effectiveness in school management and reform implementation. Their research underscores that higher academic qualifications enhance leadership competencies and improve decision-making among school heads.

f. Type of School

Table 7
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Type of School

TYPE OF SCHOOL	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Small	65	86.7
Medium	6	8.0
Large	4	5.3
Total	75	100.0

The table presents the respondents' school assignments: 65 (86.7%) lead small schools, 6 (8%) medium-sized schools, and 4 (5.3%) large schools, indicating that most school heads manage small schools. In DepEd, school typology is based on total enrollment, with many small schools arising from the policy of providing basic education in every barangay. This explains the prevalence of small schools, particularly in rural and

remote areas with lower population density. Despite smaller size and limited staff, school heads in these settings are expected to fulfill all leadership responsibilities outlined in the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH). The findings highlight the need for targeted capacity-building to address challenges such as multitasking, community engagement, and resource management. This aligns with Del Rosario and Boholano (2022), who found that small school leaders often juggle instructional and administrative duties due to limited personnel, though they exhibit adaptability and develop community-based solutions to overcome resource constraints.

Table 8
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Leadership Related Training for the Last Five Years

LEVEL OF TRAINING	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Division	20	26.67
Regional	17	22.67
National	38	50.67
Total	75	100.00

Table 8 presents respondents' participation in leadership-related training over the past five years: 38 (50.67%) attended national-level training, 20 (26.67%) division-level, and 17 (22.67%) regional-level training. This shows that most school heads accessed advanced capacity-building programs. In DepEd, continuous professional development is crucial for maintaining effective educational leadership. The high participation in national training suggests strong exposure to advanced leadership practices, while division and regional participation reflects cascading leadership development efforts across governance levels. This supports DepEd's commitment to competencies outlined in the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH), particularly in Domains 1, 3, and 4. DepEd also collaborates with NEAP-recognized providers to ensure training quality and relevance. These findings align with Pascua and Labrador (2023), who found that structured leadership programs enhance decision-making, instructional supervision, and stakeholder engagement. Bush and Glover (2016) further emphasize that balanced national and localized training fosters both broad policy understanding and practical, context-specific leadership competencies.

2. How competent are the School Heads as perceived by them and the teachers in terms of the five domains of the PPSSH.

a. Leading Strategically

Table 9
The Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Level of Competence in Terms of Domain 1- Leading Strategically

Domain 1 Leading Strategically	School Head		Teachers		Over-all Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation		
Vision, Mission and Core Values	2.96	Competent	3.13	Competent	3.05	Competent
School Planning and Implementation	2.45	Moderately Competent	2.26	Moderately Competent	2.36	Moderately Competent
Program Implementation and Review	2.95	Competent	3.01	Competent	2.98	Competent
Research and Innovation	2.48	Moderately Competent	2.39	Moderately Competent	2.44	Moderately Competent
Program Design and Implementation	2.92	Competent	2.86	Competent	2.89	Competent
Learner Voice	2.95	Competent	2.77	Competent	2.86	Competent
Monitoring and Evaluation Process and Tools	2.95	Competent	2.86	Competent	2.91	Competent
Over-all Weighted Mean	2.81	Competent	2.75	Competent	2.78	Competent

Table 9 presents perceptions of school heads' competence in Domain 1—Leading Strategically of the PPSSH. Both school heads and teachers rated them Competent in *Vision, Mission and Core Values* (mean 3.05), *Monitoring and Evaluation* (2.91), *Program Design and Implementation* (2.89), *Learners' Voice* (2.86), and *Program Implementation and Review* (2.98). However, they were rated Moderately Competent in *School Planning and Implementation* (2.36) and *Research and Innovation* (2.44). The overall mean was 2.78 (Competent). Domain 1 emphasizes strategic leadership in planning, innovation, and school improvement, aligned with DepEd's School-Based Management (SBM) framework. The ratings show strengths in vision communication, program management, and evaluation, but also reveal challenges in planning and research—likely due to limited training, technical support, and resources, especially in remote contexts. These findings support De Guzman and Salazar (2023), who found public school heads competent in vision alignment and evaluation but hindered by administrative workload and lack of technical support in strategic planning and innovation.

b. Managing School Operations and Resources

Table 10
The Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Level of Competence in Terms of Domain 2- Managing School Operations and Resources

Domain 2 Managing School Operations and Resources	School Head		Teachers		Over-all Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation		
Records Management	2.51	Competent	2.65	Competent	2.58	Competent
Financial Management	2.51	Competent	2.64	Competent	2.58	Competent
School Facilities and Equipment	2.52	Competent	2.75	Competent	2.64	Competent
Management of Staff	2.52	Competent	2.52	Competent	2.52	Competent
School Safety and Disaster Preparedness, Mitigation and Resiliency	2.95	Competent	2.45	Moderately Competent	2.70	Competent
Emerging Opportunities and Challenges	2.92	Competent	2.26	Moderately Competent	2.59	Competent
Over-all Weighted Mean	2.66	Competent	2.55	Competent	2.48	Competent

Table 10 presents perceptions of school heads' competence in Domain 2—Managing School Operations and Resources (PPSSH). Both school heads and teachers rated them Competent in *Records Management*, *Financial Management*, *School Facilities and Equipment*, and *Management of Staff*. However, in *School Safety and Disaster Preparedness* and *Emerging Opportunities and Challenges*, school heads rated themselves Competent, while teachers rated them Moderately Competent. The overall mean was 2.66 (school heads), 2.55 (teachers), and 2.48 combined—interpreted as Competent. Domain 2 highlights effective operational management. The perception gap in safety and emerging challenges suggests teachers may feel unprepared, possibly due to limited drills, poor protocol communication, or low involvement in planning. This highlights the need for stronger adaptive leadership, risk management, and collaboration. The findings align with Reyes and Del Mundo (2022), who found public school heads manage routine operations well but struggle with dynamic issues. Bush (2018) also stresses that disaster preparedness demands continuous training and inclusive planning to bridge these perception gaps.

c. Focusing on Teaching and Learning

Table 11
The Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Level of Competence in Terms of Domain 3- Focusing on Teaching and Learning

Domain 3 Focusing on Teaching and Learning	School Head		Teachers		Over-all Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation		
School-based Review, Contextualization and Implementation of Learning Standards	2.93	Competent	2.39	Moderately Competent	2.66	Competent
Teaching Standards and Pedagogy	2.88	Competent	2.13	Moderately Competent	2.51	Competent
Teacher Performance Feedback	2.37	Moderately Competent	2.5	Competent	2.44	Moderately Competent
Learner Achievement and Other performance Indicators	2.4	Moderately Competent	2.4	Moderately Competent	2.40	Moderately Competent
Learning Assessment	2.93	Competent	2.32	Moderately Competent	2.63	Competent
Learning Environment	2.93	Competent	2.42	Moderately Competent	2.68	Competent
Career Awareness and Opportunities	2.92	Competent	2.42	Moderately Competent	2.67	Competent
Learner Discipline	2.95	Competent	2.47	Moderately Competent	2.71	Competent
Over-all Weighted Mean	2.79	Competent	2.38	Moderately Competent	2.59	Competent

Table 11 summarizes the perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding the competence of school heads in Domain 3 – Focusing on Teaching and Learning of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH). School heads consistently rated themselves as "Competent" across various indicators, with an overall mean of 2.79, while teachers rated them as "Moderately Competent," with a mean of 2.38. This indicates a significant gap between the self-perception of school heads and the perceptions of teachers.

Areas where school heads received "Moderately Competent" ratings from both groups included Learner Achievement and Other Performance Indicators, highlighting the need for improvement in these areas. Teachers rated school heads lower in Teaching Standards and Pedagogy, Learning Assessment, and Learning Environment, suggesting a need for increased engagement and support from school heads in instructional practices and professional development.

The findings are supported by previous studies. Dando and Abad (2024) found that while many administrators demonstrated strengths in general leadership practices, their

competencies related to school planning, governance, and operational management were only rated as "satisfactory," indicating moderate competence. Similarly, in the Bulusan District, school heads were found to be moderately competent in Research and Innovation, with a mean of 2.84, where their performance declined in producing action research and achieving district-level adoption of innovations (AJHSSR, 2023).

Furthermore, Dela Cruz and Manansala (2021) highlighted that instructional leadership in public schools is often affected by competing administrative duties, hindering school heads from fully engaging in classroom observations and performance coaching. Their study emphasized the need for capacity building and time management training to help school heads balance instructional and managerial roles. Overall, these findings indicate that while school heads are generally competent, strengthening their direct engagement in the teaching and learning process is critical for sustained improvement in learner outcomes.

d. Developing Self and Others

Table 12
The Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Level of Competence in Terms of Domain 4- Developing Self and Others

Domain 4 Developing Self and Others	School Head		Teachers		Over-all Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation		
Personal and Professional	2.56	Competent	2.62	Competent	2.59	Competent
Professional Reflection and Learning	2.59	Competent	2.68	Competent	2.64	Competent
Professional Networks	2.6	Competent	2.67	Competent	2.64	Competent
Performance Management	2.6	Competent	2.57	Competent	2.59	Competent
Professional Development of Individuals and teams	2.6	Competent	2.59	Competent	2.60	Competent
Leadership Development in Individuals and Teams	2.57	Competent	2.65	Competent	2.61	Competent
General Welfare of Human Resources	2.6	Competent	2.66	Competent	2.63	Competent
Rewards and recognition System	2.59	Competent	2.74	Competent	2.67	Competent
Over-all Weighted Mean	2.59	Competent	2.65	Competent	2.62	Competent

Table 12 presents perceptions of school heads' competence in Domain 4— Developing Self and Others (PPSSH). Both school heads and teachers rated them Competent across all indicators: *Personal and Professional Development, Professional*

Reflection and Learning, Professional Networks, Performance Management, Professional Development of Individuals and Teams, Leadership Development, General Welfare of Human Resources, and Rewards and Recognition System. The overall weighted mean was 2.65 (school heads), 2.59 (teachers), and 2.62 combined. Domain 4 emphasizes fostering growth among school personnel. The results suggest school heads actively promote professional development, supported by City of Ilagan’s strong PD structure, with approved INSET and LAC sessions, and PRC-recognized PD provider status. However, *Personal and Professional Development* and *Performance Management* received the lowest ratings, indicating areas for further support. These findings align with Lepardo (2022), who found that while school heads demonstrate leadership competence, sustaining long-term development and enhancing personnel management remain key challenges impacting school climate and performance.

e. Building Connection

Table 13
The Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Level of Competence in Terms of Domain 5- Building Connection

Domain Building Connection	School Head		Teachers		Over-all Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation		
Management of Diverse Learners	2.37	Moderately Competent	2.42	Moderately Competent	2.40	Moderately Competent
Management of School organization	2.87	Competent	2.42	Moderately Competent	2.65	Competent
Inclusive Practice	2.53	Competent	2.52	Competent	2.53	Competent
Communication	2.44	Moderately Competent	2.26	Moderately Competent	2.35	Moderately Competent
Community Engagement	2.89	Competent	2.41	Moderately Competent	2.65	Competent
Over-all Weighted Mean	2.62	Competent	2.41	Moderately Competent	2.51	Competent

Table 13 highlights school heads' and teachers' perceptions of school heads' competence in Domain 5 – Building Connections of the PPSSH. Both groups rated school heads as *Moderately Competent* in Management of Diverse Learners (means: 2.37 by school heads, 2.42 by teachers) and Communication (2.44 and 2.26, respectively). In Inclusive Practice, both groups rated them *Competent* (2.53 and 2.52). School Organization showed the largest perception gap: school heads rated themselves *Competent* (2.87), while teachers rated them *Moderately Competent* (2.42). A similar gap

was found in Community Engagement (2.89 by school heads vs. 2.41 by teachers). Overall, school heads rated themselves *Competent* (2.62), while teachers gave a *Moderately Competent* rating (2.41), with a combined mean of 2.51. These gaps suggest differing views on leadership effectiveness. The findings echo those of Reyes and Magpili (2021), who noted communication challenges in school leadership, and De Guzman and Salazar (2022), who emphasized the role of community collaboration in school improvement.

Table 14
Summary of the Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Level of Competence in Terms of the Five Domains of the PPSSH

Domain	School Heads (WM)	Interpretation	Teachers (WM)	Interpretation	Overall Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Leading Strategically	2.81	Competent	2.75	Competent	2.78	Competent
2. Managing School Operations and Resources	2.66	Competent	2.55	Competent	2.48	Competent
3. Focusing on Teaching and Learning	2.79	Competent	2.38	Competent	2.59	Competent
4. Developing Self and Others	2.59	Competent	2.65	Competent	2.62	Competent
5. Building Connections	2.62	Competent	2.41	Competent	2.51	Competent
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN					2.596	Competent

Table 14 presents the summary of the Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Level of Competence in Terms of the Five Domains of the PPSSH. Table above reflects the rating of both School Heads and Teachers on the five domains of the PPSSH, it can be gleaned from the table that the two group of respondents have similar rating in all the domains. The consistent “Competent” ratings given by both school heads and teachers across all five domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH) may be attributed to the aligned understanding and appreciation of leadership practices guided by this national framework. The alignment in perceptions between school heads and teachers regarding the school heads' competence across all five domains can be substantiated by empirical studies.

Estrada and Gumban (2024) found a significant positive correlation between the competence of school heads and the performance of teachers, indicating that effective leadership—anchored in PPSSH—translates into observable improvements in teacher

practice, which in turn fosters mutual recognition and agreement on leadership effectiveness.

Similarly, Dando (2024) revealed that school heads in the Labo East District were rated “Very Satisfactory” to “Outstanding” in domains such as Leading Strategically, Managing School Operations, and Focusing on Teaching and Learning. These strong performance outcomes contribute to the consistent “Competent” evaluations, as both leaders and teachers observe the tangible results of sound school leadership.

Complementing these findings, Delavin (2023) highlighted how school heads progress through career stages aligned with the PPSSH, reinforcing continuous professional development and the deepening of leadership competencies over time. This structured and developmental approach fosters consistent application of leadership standards, which both school heads and teachers can readily recognize and affirm in practice. Furthermore, the PPSSH framework emphasizes collaborative leadership and stakeholder engagement, fostering an environment where teachers are actively involved in decision-making processes. This inclusive approach enhances transparency and mutual understanding, leading to aligned perceptions of leadership effectiveness.

3. Is there a significant difference on the leadership competence of the School Heads as perceived by them and the teachers.

Table 15
Significant Difference on the Leadership Competence of the School Heads Perceived by Them and Teachers

Group	Mean	Significance <i>F</i>	Decision	Remarks
School Heads	2.64	.36	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference
Teachers	2.55			

Table 15 shows the significant difference on the leadership competence of the School Heads as perceived by them and the teachers using Analysis of Variance *F* -test at .05 level of significance.

As shown, the significance *F* -value between the group of School Heads and teachers is greater than .05 which resulted to the acceptance of null hypothesis *H*₀. This statistically indicates that there is no significant difference on the leadership competence of the School Heads as perceived by them and the teachers. Hence, the School Heads and teachers perceived equally how competent are the School Heads in leading their respective school community.

The acceptance of the **null hypothesis** suggests that there is **no significant difference** in the perception of leadership competence between school heads and teachers. This means that both groups **equally perceive the leadership competence** of school heads across all five domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH). The consistency in their ratings reflects a **shared understanding and agreement** regarding how school heads perform their leadership roles.

This finding aligns with the study of Briones (2020), which emphasized that effective school leadership is better recognized when there is mutual agreement and shared perception between leaders and their stakeholders, particularly teachers.

Likewise, Medallon and Fernandez (2021) noted in their comparative study on school leadership perceptions that minimal discrepancies between school heads and teachers indicate effective communication, transparency, and alignment of leadership behaviors to expected standards.

Furthermore, Alviator (2019) asserted that shared leadership perceptions reflect a healthy school culture, where leaders are visible, participative, and responsive to the needs of the learning community. These studies reinforce the idea that alignment in perception is a strong indicator of cohesive school leadership and collaborative school management.

4. Is there a significant difference on the leadership competence of the School Heads when grouped according to their profile.

Table 16
Significant Difference on the Leadership Competence of the School Heads when grouped according to Their Profile

Profile	Significance <i>F</i>	Decision	Remarks
Age	.463	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference
Gender	.483	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference
Position Title	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Difference
Number of Years as School Head	.045	Reject Ho	There is Significant Difference
Educational Attainment	160	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference
Type of School	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Difference

Table 16 shows that age, gender, and educational attainment do not significantly affect the leadership competence of school heads, as indicated by F-values greater than .05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. In contrast, position, years of experience as a school head, and type of school significantly impact leadership competence, as shown by F-values less than .05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Specifically, Principal III school heads, those with 4–6 years of experience, and those managing medium-sized schools demonstrated higher competence.

This aligns with Rios and Corpuz (2023), who found no significant correlation between school heads' demographic variables and their e-leadership skills. It also supports Aguilar (2023), Acera and Tan (2023), and Dando and Abad (2024), who reported that professional experience, leadership position, and school type are critical factors influencing leadership competence. Collectively, these findings suggest that while demographic factors are less influential, professional roles and school contexts play a significant role in shaping effective school leadership.

5. How serious are the challenges encountered by the School Heads in the performance of their duties and responsibilities along the five domains of the PPSSH.

- a. Leading Strategically

Table 17
The Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Degree of Seriousness of the Challenges Encountered in Terms of Domain 1- Leading Strategically

Domain 1 Leading Strategically	School Head		Teachers		Over-all Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation		
Vision, Mission and Core Values	1.21	Not Serious	1.21	Not Serious	1.21	Not Serious
School Planning and Implementation	1.84	Moderately Serious	1.76	Moderately Serious	1.8	Moderately Serious
Program Implementation and Review	1.65	Not Serious	1.53	Not Serious	1.59	Not Serious
Research and Innovation	2.41	Moderately Serious	1.76	Moderately Serious	2.09	Moderately Serious

Program Design and Implementation	1.61	Not Serious	1.48	Not Serious	1.55	Not Serious
Learner Voice	1.59	Not Serious	1.36	Not Serious	1.48	Not Serious
Monitoring and Evaluation Process and Tools	1.73	Not Serious	1.47	Not Serious	1.60	Not Serious
Over-all Weighted Mean	1.72	Not Serious	1.51	Not Serious	1.62	Not Serious

Table 17 shows that both school heads and teachers generally perceive the challenges in Domain 1 – Leading Strategically as *Not Serious*, with the exception of School Planning and Implementation and Research and Innovation, which were rated *Moderately Serious*. Specifically, Vision, Mission, and Core Values; Program Implementation and Review; Program Design and Implementation; Learner Voice; and Monitoring and Evaluation were consistently seen as *Not Serious*, indicating these areas are relatively well-managed. However, School Planning and Implementation and particularly Research and Innovation present moderate concerns, suggesting a need for greater focus and improvement in these aspects of leadership.

This is supported by Vega and Tanuan (2020), who found that effective school planning and innovation are often hindered by limited resources, insufficient professional development, and resistance to change. Their study emphasized that while schools value innovation and strategic planning, practical challenges in implementation persist, underscoring the need for sustained professional learning, collaboration, and supportive school culture to overcome these barriers.

b. Managing School Operations and Resources

Table 18
The Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Degree of Seriousness of the Challenges Encountered in Terms of Domain 2- Managing School Operations and Resources

Domain 2 Managing School Operations and Resources	School Head		Teachers		Over-all Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation		
Records Management	1.79	Moderately Serious	1.87	Moderately Serious	1.83	Moderately Serious

Financial Management	1.57	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious	1.51	Not Serious
School Facilities and Equipment	1.57	Not Serious	1.51	Not Serious	1.54	Not Serious
Management of Staff	1.56	Not Serious	1.47	Not Serious	1.52	Not Serious
School Safety and Disaster Preparedness, Mitigation and Resiliency	1.69	Not Serious	1.29	Not Serious	1.49	Not Serious
Emerging Opportunities and Challenges	1.75	Moderately Serious	1.35	Not Serious	1.55	Not Serious
Over-all Weighted Mean	1.66	Not Serious	1.49	Not Serious	1.58	Not Serious

Table 18 presents the perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding the seriousness of challenges under Domain 2: *Managing School Operations and Resources*. Both groups rated Records Management as *Moderately Serious* (school heads: 1.79; teachers: 1.87), highlighting a common concern in this area. Conversely, they rated the following areas as *Not Serious*: Financial Management (school heads: 1.57; teachers: 1.45), School Facilities and Equipment (1.57; 1.51), Management of Staff (1.56; 1.47), and School Safety and Disaster Preparedness (1.69; 1.29). For Emerging Opportunities and Challenges, school heads gave a *Moderately Serious* rating (1.75), while teachers rated it *Not Serious* (1.35), indicating differing perspectives.

The overall weighted means were 1.66 for school heads and 1.49 for teachers, with a combined mean of 1.58—all interpreted as *Serious*. However, the general trend suggests that both groups perceive most challenges in this domain as *Not Serious*, except for Records Management and, for school heads, Emerging Opportunities and Challenges. These findings align with Ferrer and Castillo (2022), who noted ongoing issues in school records management, particularly regarding accuracy, regulatory compliance, and limited digital integration—especially in resource-constrained schools. They emphasized the need for professional development and a more systematic approach to records handling. Similarly, Bautista and Tan (2023) discussed the dual nature of emerging challenges and opportunities in education. They observed that while some school leaders embrace innovations spurred by technological shifts and demographic changes, others struggle due to limited resources, inadequate training, and internal resistance. Their study highlights the importance of adaptability and strategic leadership in responding to such evolving demands.

c. Focusing on Teaching and Learning

Table 19
The Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Degree of Seriousness of the Challenges Encountered in Terms of Domain 3- Focusing on teaching and Learning

Domain 3 Focusing on Teaching and Learning	School Head		Teachers		Over-all Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation		
School-based Review, Contextualization and Implementation of Learning Standards	2.00	Moderately Serious	1.75	Moderately Serious	1.88	Moderately Serious
Teaching Standards and Pedagogy	1.88	Moderately Serious	1.92	Moderately Serious	1.90	Moderately Serious
Teacher Performance Feedback	1.53	Not Serious	1.52	Not Serious	1.53	Not Serious
Learner Achievement and Other performance Indicators	1.52	Not Serious	1.79	Moderately Serious	1.66	Not Serious
Learning Assessment	1.69	Not Serious	1.72	Not Serious	1.71	Not Serious
Learning Environment	1.51	Not Serious	1.48	Not Serious	1.50	Not Serious
Career Awareness and Opportunities	1.69	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious	1.57	Not Serious
Learner Discipline	1.55	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious	1.50	Not Serious
Over-all Weighted Mean	1.67	Not Serious	1.64	Not Serious	1.66	Not Serious

Table 19 illustrates the perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding the seriousness of challenges in Domain 3: Focusing on Teaching and Learning. Both groups rated School-based Review and Contextualization and Implementation of Learning Standards as Moderately Serious, with school heads scoring 2.0 and teachers 1.75. Similarly, Teaching Standards and Pedagogy were rated as Moderately Serious (1.88 for school heads and 1.92 for teachers). However, challenges such as Teacher Performance Feedback, Learning Assessment, Learning Environment, and Career Awareness were rated as Not Serious, with scores ranging from 1.45 to 1.72. Notably, in Learner Achievement and Other Performance Indicators, school heads rated this as Not Serious (1.52), while teachers rated it as Moderately Serious (1.79). The overall weighted means were 1.67 for school heads, 1.64 for teachers, and 1.66 combined, interpreted as Not Serious.

The data indicates that while school heads and teachers perceive certain areas, particularly curriculum contextualization and teaching standards, as moderately serious, most challenges in this domain are considered not serious. This perception may stem from the Department of Education's ongoing initiatives, such as the Learning Action Cell

(LAC) and the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS), which enhance the capacity of both teachers and school heads to address instructional challenges. The differing views on learner achievement suggest that teachers may be more aware of academic performance gaps due to their direct involvement in teaching, whereas school heads may prioritize overall school outcomes.

Supporting these findings, Ballado-Tan (2022) noted that instructional leadership challenges are generally manageable among public school heads, focusing on contextualization practices and teaching standards. Pascual and Llego (2021) also found that continuous professional development through NEAP-recognized programs has alleviated concerns in teaching and learning, with regular LAC sessions and consistent RPMS monitoring fostering a culture of professional growth and accountability.

d. Developing Self and Others

Table 20
The Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Degree of Seriousness of the Challenges Encountered in Terms of Domain 4- Developing Self and Others

Domain 4 Developing Self and Others	School Head		Teachers		Over-all Waighted Mean	Interpretation
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation		
Personal and Professional Development	1.65	Not Serious	1.35	Not Serious	1.5	Not Serious
Professional Reflection and Learning	1.71	Not Serious	1.43	Not Serious	1.57	Not Serious
Professional Networks	1.59	Not Serious	1.48	Not Serious	1.54	Not Serious
Performance Management	1.81	Moderately Serious	1.52	Not Serious	1.67	Not Serious
Professional Development of School Personnel	1.69	Not Serious	1.49	Not Serious	1.59	Not Serious
Leadership Development in Individuals and Teams	1.79	Moderately Serious	1.44	Not Serious	1.62	Not Serious
General Welfare of Human Resources	1.52	Not Serious	1.52	Not Serious	1.52	Not Serious
Rewards and recognition System	1.65	Not Serious	1.35	Not Serious	1.50	Not Serious

Over-all Weighted Mean	1.68	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious	1.56	Not Serious
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Table 20 details the perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding the seriousness of challenges in Domain 4: Developing Self and Others. Both groups rated various aspects as Not Serious, including Personal and Professional (1.65 for school heads, 1.35 for teachers), Professional Reflection and Learning (1.71 for school heads, 1.43 for teachers), and Professional Networks (1.59 for school heads, 1.48 for teachers). However, school heads rated Performance Management (1.81) and Leadership Development in Individuals and Teams (1.79) as Moderately Serious, while teachers rated these areas as Not Serious (1.52 and 1.44, respectively). The overall weighted means were 1.68 for school heads, 1.45 for teachers, and 1.59 combined, interpreted as Not Serious.

These results indicate that both school heads and teachers generally do not perceive significant challenges in this domain. The higher ratings for Performance Management and Leadership Development may reflect the increasing administrative duties of school leaders in staff evaluation and motivation amid changing educational contexts. The low ratings across most indicators could be attributed to the regular implementation of in-service training (INSETs), Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions, and professional development activities mandated by DepEd Order No. 009, s. 2024. The City of Ilagan's accreditation as a Professional Development (PD) provider by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) and the National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP) further supports this continuous growth for educators.

The findings align with De Leon and Santos (2023), who found that schools with strong support systems report fewer challenges in professional and leadership development due to consistent engagement in recognized training. Ramirez and Tolentino (2022) noted that PD providers foster systematic leadership development, making performance management and leadership tasks more manageable. Cabrera (2021) emphasized that effective implementation of DepEd policies significantly minimizes leadership-related challenges, resulting in greater confidence and effectiveness among school heads in developing their teams.

e. Building Connection

Table 21
The Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Degree of Seriousness of the Challenges Encountered in Terms of Domain 5- Building Connection

Domain Building Connection	School Head		Teachers		Over-all Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation		
Management of Diverse Learners	2.15	Moderately Serious	1.75	Moderately Serious	1.95	Moderately Serious
Management of School organization	1.65	Not Serious	1.76	Moderately Serious	1.71	Not Serious
Inclusive Practice	1.49	Not Serious	1.41	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious
Communication	1.64	Not Serious	1.92	Moderately Serious	1.78	Moderately Serious
Community Engagement	1.70	Not Serious	1.83	Moderately Serious	1.77	Moderately Serious
Over-all Weighted Mean	1.73	Not Serious	1.73	Not Serious	1.73	Not Serious

Table 21 presents the perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding the seriousness of challenges in Domain 5: Building Connection. Both groups rated Management of Diverse Learners as Moderately Serious, with school heads scoring 2.15 and teachers 1.75. However, they rated Inclusive Practice as Not Serious (1.49 for school heads, 1.41 for teachers). A notable perception gap exists where school heads rated Management of School Organization (1.65), Communication (1.64), and Community Engagement (1.70) as Not Serious, while teachers rated these as Moderately Serious (1.76, 1.92, and 1.83, respectively). The overall weighted mean for Domain 5 is 1.73 for both groups, interpreted as Not Serious.

The data reveals a significant perception gap, indicating that while both groups generally view the challenges as Not Serious, teachers find issues like Communication and Community Engagement more pressing. This suggests that school heads may prioritize broader organizational concerns, while teachers focus on daily interactions with the community. The moderate seriousness attributed to Management of Diverse Learners reflects a shared acknowledgment of its importance, yet the overall Not Serious categorization may underestimate the impact of these challenges, particularly regarding community ties and communication.

These findings align with De Guzman and Tolentino (2023), who noted teachers feel overwhelmed by insufficient support for managing diverse learners. Similarly, Lee and Cho (2023) emphasized the need for strategic approaches and adequate resources for managing diverse classrooms. Both studies highlight the need for targeted leadership and resource allocation to support teachers effectively, reinforcing the current study's findings.

Table 22
Summary of the Perception of the School Heads and Teachers on the School Heads Degree of Seriousness of the Challenges in terms of the Five Domains of the PPSSH

Domain`	School Heads (WM)	Interpretation	Teachers (WM)	Interpretation	Overall Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Leading Strategically	1.72	Not Serious	1.51	Not Serious	1.62	Not Serious
2. Managing School Operations and Resources	1.66	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious	1.57	Not Serious
3. Focusing on Teaching and Learning	1.67	Not Serious	1.64	Not Serious	1.65	Not Serious
4. Developing Self and Others	1.68	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious	1.56	Not Serious
5. Building Connections	1.73	Not Serious	1.73	Not Serious	1.73	Not Serious
Overall Weighted Mean					1.626	Not Serious

Table 22 summarizes the perceptions of school heads and teachers in the City of Ilagan regarding the seriousness of challenges across the five domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH). Overall, the perception is "Not Serious," with a weighted mean of 1.626, indicating that both groups view the leadership challenges as manageable and not urgent. This consistent viewpoint across all

domains—from strategic leadership to building connections—may stem from robust support systems, effective leadership practices, and professional development programs that empower school heads and teachers.

These findings contrast with Castañeros et al. (2023), who highlighted challenges like inadequate training and role ambiguity for newly promoted school heads, suggesting that such issues could be better addressed through ongoing professional development. Lochmiller et al. (2024) noted that supportive leadership practices significantly influence teacher retention, a concern not perceived as serious in Ilagan, potentially due to a positive school climate. Similarly, Zadok et al. (2024) emphasized transformational leadership's role in fostering resilience, which may explain why Ilagan educators perceive challenges as less serious, aided by leadership that enhances teacher efficacy and collaboration.

Nguyen et al. (2024) found that promoting professional collaboration leads to improved outcomes, aligning with the PPSSH's focus on collaboration. Additionally, a synthesis on mental health and leadership during crises (2024) underscores the importance of leadership in supporting well-being. Together, these studies suggest that strong transformational and supportive leadership minimizes perceived challenges, creating an environment conducive to addressing leadership issues and explaining the relatively low seriousness ratings in Ilagan compared to other regions.

6. Is there a significant difference on the challenges encountered by the School heads in the performance of their duties and responsibilities when grouped according to their profile.

Table 23
Result of Significant Difference on the Challenges Encountered by the School Heads in the Performance of Duties and Responsibilities when grouped according to Their Profile

Profile	Significance <i>F</i>	Decision	Remarks
Age	.305	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference
Gender	.155	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference
Position Title	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Difference
Number of Years as School Head	.127	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference
Educational Attainment	.795	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference
Type of School	.065	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference

Table 23 presents the results of an Analysis of Variance F-test examining the challenges faced by school heads in performing their duties, revealing significant differences based on their profile. The F-values for age, gender, years of service as a school head, educational attainment, and type of school were all greater than .05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating no significant difference in challenges based on these demographic factors. However, for the profile position, the F-values were less than .05, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis, suggesting that the challenges faced by school heads differ significantly based on their position.

The findings indicate that challenges are more influenced by the position of the school heads rather than demographic factors. Specifically, those in higher positions, such as Principal 2 and Principal 3, experience more complex challenges due to their broader responsibilities and greater decision-making authority. This complexity likely arises from overseeing larger teams, implementing policy changes, and addressing intricate school-level issues. In contrast, factors like age and years of experience appear to have a lesser impact on the nature of these challenges.

These results align with Leithwood and Sun (2023), who found that higher-ranking school leaders encounter more complex challenges related to their extensive responsibilities. Similarly, Tingzon and Santos (2024) noted that senior school heads are more involved in strategic planning and resource allocation, reinforcing the notion that position significantly shapes the challenges faced by school leaders.

7. Do the challenges encountered by the School Heads significantly affect their leadership competence.

Table 24
Significant Effect of the Challenges Encountered by the School Heads to Their Leadership Competence

Group	Mean	Significance <i>R</i>	Decision	Remarks
Challenges encountered by the School Heads	2.53	.000	Reject H_0	There is Significant Effect
Leadership competence of School Heads	2.10			

Table 23 presents the significant effect of the challenges encountered by the School Heads to their leadership competence using Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation r -test at .05 level of significance.

Revealed in table, the significance r -value between the group challenges encountered by the School Heads and their leadership competence is less than .05 which resulted to the rejection of null hypothesis H_0 . This statistically indicates that there is a significant effect of the challenges encountered by the School Heads to their leadership

competence. Hence, the leadership competence of School Heads is significantly affected by the challenges they encountered in leading their respective school community.

The analysis indicates that the challenges encountered by school heads have a significant effect on their leadership competence. The rejection of the null hypothesis, based on the Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation r -test, suggests that the relationship between the challenges faced and the leadership competence of school heads is statistically significant. This implies that the difficulties experienced in managing school operations, handling diverse learners, and addressing various administrative and interpersonal issues directly influence the effectiveness and skills of school heads in performing their leadership roles. The challenges may either strengthen or hinder their leadership capabilities, depending on how these challenges are managed and mitigated. The finding underscores the importance of providing adequate support and resources to school heads to help them overcome these challenges, thereby enhancing their leadership competence and overall effectiveness in school management.

These findings are supported by existing research that underscores the significant relationship between the challenges encountered by school heads and their leadership competence. Bush and Glover (2022) assert that school leaders' ability to navigate challenges such as resource allocation, teacher performance, and school climate is directly linked to their effectiveness in leadership.

Day and Leithwood (2023) emphasize that leadership challenges related to school operations and community engagement play a critical role in shaping a leader's competence, especially when such challenges are effectively managed.

Garcia and Corderob (2023) highlight that the leadership challenges faced by school heads significantly influence their performance, particularly in managing school resources and enhancing the learning environment. These studies collectively support the notion that the leadership competence of school heads is shaped by the challenges they face in key leadership domains, reinforcing the findings of this study.

Conclusions

The findings of this study highlight that school heads in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan demonstrate overall competence in their leadership roles across the five domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH). However, gaps exist in specific areas, particularly in strategic planning, instructional leadership, and research innovation, which require further professional development.

While most challenges encountered by school heads were perceived as not serious, certain aspects, such as curriculum contextualization, leadership development, communication, and managing diverse learners, were identified as moderately challenging. These challenges, although not overwhelming, significantly impact the effectiveness of school leadership, particularly for those in higher positions such as Principal 2 and Principal 3.

Ultimately, the study concludes that while school heads are equipped with the essential leadership competencies, ongoing support systems, targeted training, and capacity-building initiatives are crucial in bridging existing gaps, strengthening leadership effectiveness, and addressing evolving educational challenges.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed for the key stakeholders.

Education Supervisors:

- Education Supervisors should provide consistent and proactive guidance to school heads. Regular feedback on school operations, leadership challenges, and management practices would help school heads navigate difficulties more effectively.
- Education supervisors should facilitate the creation of professional learning communities among school heads. These communities would provide school heads with opportunities to share experiences, discuss challenges, and collaborate on solutions to common issues.
- Supervisors should provide personalized support to school heads, particularly those struggling with specific leadership challenges. Tailored advice and resources could be provided to help school heads address issues related to school management, community engagement, and curriculum implementation.

Curriculum Implementation Division (CID) Chief:

- The CID Chief should ensure that curriculum implementation strategies are inclusive and flexible, addressing the diverse learning needs of students. The curriculum should be adaptable to suit the challenges of managing diverse learners and fostering an inclusive school environment.
- The CID Chief should work closely with school heads to ensure that curriculum delivery aligns with the identified leadership challenges. School heads should be provided with the necessary resources, training, and support to effectively implement the curriculum in their respective schools.
- The CID Chief should collaborate with the HRTD to offer regular training programs focused on effective curriculum implementation. These programs should cover topics such as curriculum adaptation, managing learning resources, and fostering an inclusive learning environment.

Schools Division Superintendent:

- The Schools Division Superintendent should ensure that adequate resources are allocated for continuous leadership development programs for school heads. This includes collaborating with the HRTD and other divisions to design professional development sessions that address the unique leadership challenges identified in this study.
- **Focus on Collaborative Networks:** The Schools Division Superintendent should prioritize the establishment of collaborative networks for school heads, fostering peer support and shared learning. This would allow school heads to exchange

strategies, share challenges, and work together to find effective solutions to common problems.

- The Schools Division Superintendent should advocate for the inclusion of leadership development as a core component of school management policy. This includes securing additional resources for training, mentoring, and coaching, as well as ensuring that school heads are supported in their efforts to overcome leadership challenges.
- The Schools Division Superintendent should explore partnerships with universities and other educational institutions to offer advanced degrees or certification programs for school heads. These programs would focus on enhancing leadership competencies in line with the challenges faced by school heads.
- The Schools Division Superintendent should initiate partnerships with the Local Government Units (LGUs) to provide scholarship programs for school heads who wish to pursue Master's Degree and PhD programs. These programs would further enhance the academic and leadership qualifications of school heads, enabling them to effectively address the complex challenges of school leadership.

School Heads:

- School heads should actively engage in professional development opportunities that are tailored to addressing the challenges identified in this study. Specifically, they should focus on improving their leadership skills in areas such as communication, inclusive practices, and managing diverse learners.
- School heads should prioritize the creation of a collaborative school environment. This includes promoting open lines of communication, seeking regular feedback from teachers and staff, and involving them in decision-making processes. This collaborative approach can help address leadership challenges more effectively.
- School heads should develop strategic plans that address both short-term and long-term challenges in school management. They should focus on optimizing resource management and ensuring that their schools are equipped to meet the diverse needs of students.
- School heads should actively participate in networks and forums with other school heads to exchange best practices and solutions for common leadership challenges. Peer support can be an invaluable resource for overcoming challenges.

Human Resource and Training Division (HRTD):

- The HRTD should develop and implement training programs specifically targeting the leadership challenges identified in this study, such as managing diverse learners, inclusive practices, and communication. These programs should be context-specific, addressing the needs of school heads in varying school settings.
- The HRTD should consider establishing mentorship or coaching programs that pair experienced school heads with those in higher leadership positions (e.g., Principal 2 and Principal 3). These programs would provide ongoing support and guidance, particularly in addressing the complex challenges faced by school leaders.
- Regular follow-up assessments should be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the training programs. Feedback from school heads should be incorporated into

future program designs to ensure their relevance and effectiveness in meeting the evolving needs of school leaders.

The Researcher:

In light of the findings of this study on the leadership competence and challenges of school heads in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, the researcher strongly recommends the formal presentation of the research results and the proposed intervention program to the Schools Division Office. This presentation will serve as a vital step toward evidence-based decision-making and policy enhancement within the Division. The proposed dissemination should include:

- A results-sharing session with the Schools Division Superintendent, Principal-In-Charge (PICs), and key education program specialists;
- A clear presentation of the study's major findings per PPSSH domain, supported by data-driven insights;
- The formal proposal of the Upgrading Intervention Program, including its objectives, components, implementation plan, and alignment with DepEd's thrusts and PPSSH domains;
- An open forum to gather feedback from Division stakeholders and align the program with the current needs and available resources.

Future Researchers:

- Future researchers should conduct longitudinal studies to examine how leadership competence evolves over time as school heads continue to face various challenges. This type of research would provide insights into the long-term impact of leadership challenges on school heads' effectiveness and performance.
- Future studies should explore the specific leadership challenges faced by school heads in different sectors (public, private, or alternative education). This would help understand how leadership practices differ across educational settings and what unique challenges are encountered.
- Researchers could investigate how external factors such as government policies, community support, and societal changes impact the challenges faced by school heads and their leadership competence. This would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the broader context within which school heads operate.

By implementing these recommendations, school heads in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan can further enhance their leadership effectiveness, overcome challenges, and ensure sustainable and high-quality education for their learners. Continuous **leadership training, mentorship, and stakeholder engagement** will ensure **better school performance and long-term educational success**.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher made sure that during the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the Division Office, and other concerned offices for the study;
2. The researcher also acknowledged the Department of Education and the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan for allowing her to conduct the study;
3. The researcher informed the respondents of the study through letters and a short orientation to the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality;
4. The researcher, properly cited gathered information and other relevant studies from authors, books, or any publications through proper citation.

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